

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN MEDITERRANEAN SEMI-ARID REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

The Mediterranean basin is distinctly vulnerable to climate change and its associated effects. This vulnerability is noticeably observed in the southern Mediterranean territories, where a perceptible outcome of climate change is the increase of the average temperatures over time, accompanied by water scarcity result of reduced precipitation. Although recent technological advancements have achieved to mitigate climate change impacts, particularly in stabilizing temperatures and enhancing water resource management, alterations in weather patterns persist. This study presents an examination of the climate change scenario in the southern European Mediterranean nations, namely Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, and Spain, along with select semi-arid regions like Crete, Murcia, and Sicily, spotlighting data spanning the last three decades. This study seeks to outline the principal meteorological factors associated with climate change, aiming to foster a broader understanding of its impacts. Additionally, this discussion explores the potential for these regions to utilize the current climatic conditions beneficially, by pivoting towards energy production from alternative, sustainable sources, thereby converting the challenges posed by climate change into opportunities for societal benefit.

Keywords: Mediterranean Climate, Semi-arid Regions, Climate Change Adaptation, Sustainable Energy Transition, Climate Resilience

INTRODUCTION

Climate change has been casting a growing shadow over the Mediterranean regions, presenting a suite of environmental challenges that are expected to escalate in the coming years. The Mediterranean is particularly sensitive to climatic alterations, with the region warming 20% faster than the global average, underscoring the urgency of understanding and mitigating the multifaceted impacts unfolding across these landscapes [1]. A significant aspect of climate change in the Mediterranean is the rise in mean temperature. This warming trend is anticipated to continue, with air temperatures in the region expected to increase between 1.5 to 4 °C 0.5 and 2.5 °C per century [2].

The burgeoning temperature augments the frequency and severity of heat waves, which have been correlated with a notable rise in mortality rates. For instance, a study revealed that heat waves could lead to a 24.6% increase in total mortality, and a substantial increase in cardiovascular and respiratory mortalities. Such scenarios are particularly pronounced in Mediterranean cities, where urban warming exacerbates the thermal stress on human health, elevating the risks of hospitalizations and fatalities [3].

On the other hand, the rise in temperature is accompanied by a decrease in precipitation, which is predicted to fall by up to 30% in Southern Europe under a scenario of 2°C to 4°C global warming. The reduction in precipitation is a harbinger of growing water scarcity, a pressing concern especially in semi-arid and arid environments of the Mediterranean, where water is a linchpin for sustainable development. The frequent droughts experienced in the region are a testament to the escalating water crisis, which imperils not just the ecological integrity but also the socio-economic fabric of these regions[4].

In the middle of these challenges, the abundant sunny days characteristic of the Mediterranean climate become a significant resource. The investment in photovoltaic power systems to harness this solar potential is not merely an alternative but a pivotal strategy for mitigating some of the adverse impacts of climate change. Solar PV installations provide a conduit for clean, renewable energy generation, which is integral in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, a primary driver of global warming and climate change. The solar infrastructure can also contribute to water conservation by reducing the rate of evaporation, a significant benefit in water-scarce regions. Moreover, the synergy of solar PV panels with vegetation underneath can act as an effective measure against wind erosion in sandy ecosystems, showcasing a blend of ecological and economic benefits [5] [6].

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN EUROPEAN MEDITERRANEAN COUNTRIES

The analysis below delves into an examination of temperature patterns, as shown in Figure 1, across five Mediterranean nations over a quarter-century duration, presenting the potential sign of global warming in this region [7]. The chart delineates a pattern where the mean temperature for each country follows a sinusoidal trend, peaking approximately every three years and reaching a low point every five to six years. There's a noticeable trend of increasing temperatures over time across all five countries, which could be indicative of global warming's local effects. For instance, Malta's average temperature increased from 19.29°C in 1998 to 20.28°C in 2021, and similarly, Cyprus saw an increase from 19.08°C to 19.84°C over the same period. Among the five countries, Malta and Cyprus generally exhibit higher average temperatures compared to Greece, Italy, and Spain. The highest average temperature recorded within this period is 20.35°C in Cyprus during 2010, while the lowest is 12.52°C in Italy during 2005. It's notable that the peak temperatures for Malta, Cyprus, and Spain were recorded in the later years (2018-2021), aligning with global trends of rising temperatures.

The figure 2 illustrates a comparison between different Mediterranean countries in terms of their maximum temperatures, populations and, total death counts in 2022 [8]. Malta, with the smallest population of 0.52 million and a high max temperature of 41.5°C, has the highest death rate per 100,000 at 28. Despite having one of the higher

maximum temperatures and a large population of 59.11 million, Italy maintains a relatively low death rate of 0.5 per 100,000 individuals.

Figure 1. Mean Temperature in a 25-year period, by country

Figure 2. Heat-related mortality rate in Europe during the summer of 2022, by country

Climate change has intensified various environmental challenges, among which the increased frequency of wildfires stands prominent. Elevated temperatures, predominantly manifesting in the summer months, not only exert an indirect influence but also bear direct consequences on the ecosystem. The rising thermometers significantly contribute to fire outbreaks, consequently inflicting damage on the region's flora and fauna. Beyond the environmental impact, these blazes pose severe threats to human communities, resulting in substantial property loss and, tragically, loss of life. This cascade of adversities underscores the imperative of addressing the root causes of climate change to foster a more resilient and sustainable future. In Table 1, are presented the burned and the total forest areas per year from 2010 to 2023 in Cyprus, Greece, Italy and Spain [8].

Table 1. Area (in hectares) burned by wildfires from 2010 to 2023, by country

CYPRUS				GREECE		
YEAR	BURNED	TOTAL	NORM.	BURNED	TOTAL	NORM.
2010	1104	172840	0.6	6472	4132098	0.2
2011	939	172814	0.5	35713	4125626	0.9
2012	2349	172788	1.4	52487	4089913	1.3
2013	2834	172762	1.6	19762	4037426	0.5
2014	436	172736	0.3	14815	4017664	0.4
2015	197	172710	0.1	11613	4002849	0.3
2016	2738	172610	1.6	31707	3991236	0.8
2017	652	172590	0.4	20041	3959529	0.5
2018	417	172570	0.2	12037	3939488	0.3
2019	596	172550	0.3	10736	3927451	0.3
2020	3421	172530	2.0	14915	3916715	0.4
2021	6199	172510	3.6	130744	3901800	3.4
2022	2540	169970	1.5	22480	3771056	0.6
2023	1122	168848	0.7	52801	3748576	1.4
ITALY				SPAIN		
YEAR	BURNED	TOTAL	NORM.	BURNED	TOTAL	NORM.
2010	34280	10090954	0.3	19770	19289250	0.10
2011	36997	10056674	0.4	60060	19269480	0.31
2012	82856	10019677	0.8	189376	19209420	0.99
2013	15776	9936821	0.2	37069	19020044	0.19
2014	13176	9921045	0.1	22001	18982975	0.12
2015	7773	9907869	0.1	63560	18960974	0.34
2016	35246	9900096	0.4	52644	18897414	0.28
2017	140214	9864850	1.4	130925	18844770	0.69
2018	14002	9724636	0.1	12433	18713845	0.07
2019	36887	9710634	0.4	63853	18701412	0.34
2020	53807	9673747	0.6	61099	18637559	0.33
2021	150552	9619940	1.6	84827	18576460	0.46
2022	58751	9469388	0.6	306555	18491633	1.66
2023	58031	9410637	0.6	71271	18185078	0.39

IMPACT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN SEMI-ARID REGIONS

The semi-arid regions of the Mediterranean, such as Cyprus, Malta, Sicily, Crete, and Murcia [9], are characterized by their distinct climatic conditions, embodying warm to hot summers and mild winters [10], as illustrated in Table 2. Days with less than 20% cloud cover are considered as sunny. These areas are particularly susceptible to the escalating impacts of climate change, notably seen through rising maximum temperatures, decreased annual precipitation volumes, and numerous dry days throughout the year.

Table 2. 30-year meteorological data, by region

MONTH	CRETE			CYPRUS			MALTA		
	MAX (°C)	MEAN (°C)	SUNNY DAYS	MAX (°C)	MEAN (°C)	SUNNY DAYS	MAX (°C)	MEAN (°C)	SUNNY DAYS
JAN	21	15	2.8	16	11	6.2	16	14	7.7
FEB	23	16	3	18	12	4.8	14	14	6.9
MAR	26	18	4.9	22	14	7	16	14	8.7
APR	31	23	7.3	27	19	6.9	17	15	10.4
MAY	34	27	12.2	31	24	9.1	20	18	14.1
JUN	38	31	16.8	34	28	9	24	21	18.2
JUL	40	33	18.3	35	31	7.9	26	24	18.8
AUG	38	33	17.5	35	31	7.2	27	25	17.4
SEP	37	30	15.5	32	27	10.8	26	24	14.1
OCT	32	25	10	29	23	12.8	24	22	11.6
NOV	28	21	4.5	23	17	9.1	22	19	9.6
DEC	23	17	2.6	18	13	5.6	19	16	9.5
SUM	-	-	115.4	-	-	96.4	-	-	147
MONTH	MURCIA			SICILY					
	MAX (°C)	MEAN (°C)	SUNNY DAYS	MAX (°C)	MEAN (°C)	SUNNY DAYS			
JAN	21	16	13.6	17	12	4.9			
FEB	24	17	11.7	18	12	4.8			
MAR	27	19	11.4	22	15	7.2			
APR	28	22	10.1	26	18	7.4			
MAY	32	25	10	31	24	10.3			
JUN	36	29	10.5	36	30	14.9			
JUL	38	32	11.7	39	33	21.7			
AUG	38	33	11.4	39	33	19.6			
SEP	35	29	10.8	34	27	11.1			
OCT	31	25	11.8	29	23	8			
NOV	25	19	12	23	17	5.1			
DEC	22	16	13.5	18	13	4.2			
SUM	-	-	138.5	-	-	119.2			

The percentages provided in Figure 3 indicate the proportion of dry days each region experiences on an average annual basis, given a standard year of 365 days. The data underscores a notable climatic variability among these semi-arid Mediterranean regions.

Figure 3. Average annual dry days (%) over a 30-year period, by region

The Table 3 provides information about the average annual precipitation levels, in millimeters, for the same five semi-arid Mediterranean. These mean precipitation levels are defined after an observation and examination of 30-years collection of data [11] [12] [13][14]. In an analysis of meteorological patterns across the five distinct regions, compelling correlations are evident between the annual frequencies of dry days and the associated precipitation volumes. Murcia, with 335.4 dry days, exhibits the least precipitation at 309mm annually, reinforcing the apparent inverse relation between dry days and rainfall. Similarly, Crete, despite having 275.4 dry days, experiences a substantial precipitation of 967mm, indicating occasional heavy rainfall episodes. Sicily, on the other hand, has 254.4 dry days and registers a precipitation of 715mm, suggesting moderate rainfall spread throughout the year. Cyprus and Malta, with dry days tallying at 281.7 and 296 respectively, manifest almost similar precipitation volumes of 470mm and 473mm, potentially implying comparable weather patterns. These regional variations underscore the multifaceted nature of climate dynamics, emphasizing the necessity of comprehensive evaluation when interpreting such meteorological data.

Table 3. Average annual precipitation over a 30-year period, by region

REGION	CRETE	CYPRUS	MALTA	MURCIA	SICILY
PRECIPITATION	967mm	470mm	473mm	309mm	715mm

Climate change is a reality, with escalating impacts on the environment through heightened climatic and meteorological events. It's imperative for societies to adapt and mitigate these effects to ensure improved living conditions for their citizens. As depicted in the preceding diagrams, the countries mentioned are blessed with abundant sunshine throughout much of the year. This natural resource could be utilized through the use of photovoltaic (PV) panels in these countries or regions. Solar energy is not only an alternative, but a key strategy to cope with climatic adversities. The integration of solar PV systems is recognized as an important pathway for clean, renewable energy generation and plays a critical role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, the primary contributor to global warming and climate change. Additionally, solar infrastructure can aid in water conservation by “edging” evaporation rates—a lesser known yet significant benefit, especially in water-scarce regions characteristic of Mediterranean climates, as mentioned in the introduction. The figure 4 illustrates the solar energy capacity across various Mediterranean regions, with Sicily leading in solar energy capacity among the regions listed, followed by Murcia, Cyprus, Malta, and Crete. The disparity in solar

energy capacity across these regions may reflect variations in investment, governmental policies, and community engagement towards renewable energy endeavors.

Figure 4. Production of solar power, by region

CONCLUSION

This study sheds light on how the Mediterranean area is at a higher risk due to the growing impacts of climate change. Higher average temperatures and less rain are the main climate problems faced by these regions. A careful look at the climate changes in selected Mediterranean countries and dry areas over the last 30 years shows a clear warming trend. Moreover, the study points out the resulting increase in heat waves, water shortages, and wildfires, among other issues, all tied to the rise in temperature.

On a positive note, the study identifies the great solar energy potential due to the sunny weather typical of these regions. The plentiful sunlight presents a valuable chance to shift towards using sustainable energy. By tapping into this solar potential through the use of solar panels, these regions can lessen some of the negative effects of climate change and move towards a sustainable energy setup.

Furthermore, the connection between solar setups and saving water not only highlights the need to lessen greenhouse gas emissions but also moves the discussion towards finding practical solutions. By turning the challenges brought by climate change into chances for sustainable development, the Mediterranean regions can lead the way in creating a climate-strong pathway. This isn't just about reacting but planning ahead, ensuring a good quality of life and growth for their communities as the climate changes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research work was supported by the ISTOS project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (WIDESPREAD-TWINNING) under grant agreement No. 952300.

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